

Resumen

Las universidades son uno de los centros principales de producciones científicas. Las actividades de las universidades se causan la producción de los documentos y objetos que, por el valor permanente, merece la pena cuidar y conservarlos. Entonces, se han fundado los archivos y museos en las universidades para gestionar los documentos y objetos.

Los archivos académicos identifican, proporcionan y protegen documentos y objetos de valor permanente que se causan el desarrollo de la organización. Obviamente garantizan su continuidad.

Todos los documentos creados, recibidos, mantenidos o enviados por los empleados universitarios durante su trabajo en la universidad se consideran oficiales por la universidad y deben ser registrados y conservados por sistemas de gestión documental. Los documentos de archivos académicos pueden abarcar los documentos escritos y audiovisuales. Solo una sección de los documentos producidos en la universidad tiene valor histórico a largo plazo. La gran cantidad de documentos puede explicar cómo o por qué sucedió algo y puede ayudar a la comunidad con el fin de conectarse con el pasado. De hecho, los archivos académicos y los museos proporcionan pruebas para las universidades que sirvan en el futuro en investigaciones históricas o documentos y objetos legales. Por lo tanto, debido a la importancia y el valor de los archivos y museos, los documentos y objetos académicos, la Universidad de Alzahra ha puesto en marcha un museo y archivo académico. Con atención de la importancia del intercambio de experiencias, el archivo de la Universidad de Alzahra puede reflejar la manera de pensar y la cultura del archivo en Irán y también el almacenamiento de experiencias sin valor. Este artículo muestra las experiencias de esta Universidad en el establecimiento del archivo y museo académico. Además, la experiencia de la Universidad de Alzahra se ha propuesto como la primera experiencia en la creación de un archivo universitario de acuerdo con los estándares internacionales de archivo en Irán. En el primero se cuenta la historia de la Universidad de Alzahra, en el segundo lugar, se explica las medidas de la Universidad para crear el archivo y el museo.

Palabras clave: Universidad de Alzahra, Archivo Universitario, Museo Universitario, Experiencia

Establishing a university archive to preserve its memory and identity: the experience of Alzahra University

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Abstract

Universities are one of the leading centers of scientific production. Activities as a university result in producing records and objects that need to be protected and maintained for their permanent value. So archives and museums were created at universities to manage records and objects. Academic archives identify, provide, and preserve sustainable value records and objects that lead to its development and ensure its continued life. All records created, received, maintained, or sent by university staff during their work at the university are official university-based and must be recorded and supported by record management systems. Academic archives records can include written and audiovisual records. Only a small fraction of the records produced at the university each year has long-term historical value. But the sheer number of records can explain how or why something happened and help the community connect with the

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past. Academic archives and museums provide evidence for universities that may in the future be used in historical research or as legal records and objects. Therefore, due to archives and museums' importance and value and so academic records and objects, Alzahra University has established an academic archive and museum.

Given that transferring Alzahra University archives establish experiences can reflect the thinking and the archiving culture in Iran and storing worthless experiences, this article examines how this university is establishing an academic archive and museum. Also, the experience of Alzahra University has been proposed as the first experience in creating a university archive by international archival standards in Iran. The history of Alzahra University is discussed first, and then the steps that the university has taken in making the archive and museum are explained.

Keywords: *Alzahra University, University Archive, University Museum, Experience*

Introduction

Today, universities play an essential role in the production of science and the development of societies. So scientific data is an important part of any nation. On the other hand, each university's historical memory is part of every land's historical memory. Hence, universities manage their records in the form of academic archives.

Academic archives serve as the university's organizational memory and play an integral role in managing its information resources across all media and forms. Academic archives identify, provide, and protect sustainable value records that lead to the organization's development and ensure its continued life to carry out this role. The records in these archives represent the process of organizational evolution through the preservation of evidence that shapes corporate decisions (American Archives Association, 1999).

These records help historians, artists, reporters, and genealogists gain new knowledge about the university's components and the people who have worked or studied at the university (University of Michigan, 2014).

The purpose of the University Record Management is to ensure that the University staff produces and maintains the required records to enable them to access and use them efficiently and ensure that they are kept as long as possible. Operational, legal, and auditing objectives are required, maintained, and eliminated as needed (Record Management of Princeton, 2018).

Alzahra University, with its rich historical background and over one thousand archival records that demonstrate this, has the potential to create an academic archive. Therefore, Alzahra University, with the help of its archival studies graduates, has sought to establish the first Iranian university archive with archival standards.

This article reviews Alzahra University's experiences in establishing a university archive and museum over the past year.

University Archives in Iran and its Challenges

The first university in Iran was established 90 years ago. This history can be the basis for creating many records in Iranian universities. On the other hand, today, one of the most important centers of science and culture in the world is the university, which in addition to scientific missions, has effective social, political, and cultural maps and functions. This great social and cultural institution, especially in science and technology, empowers and prepares the society to dominate future events (Zaker Salehi, 2005).

Therefore, records that result from universities' activities in Iran can be important and valuable to maintain. Preliminary studies among Iranian universities show that a small number of universities have addressed their records and the importance of preserving them, and if they have taken action in this regard, it has been in the form of establishing a record center. It also seems that there is no unified policy and standard in Iran, according to international archival standards in Iran.

Therefore, this article is presented to show the action of Alzahra University to create a university archive in Iran as a new action. It is always difficult and essential to do the first ones in any scientific field and any country. Alzahra University is also one of the first standard university archives in Iran about its approach to applying archival standards, software with special archive fields, and employing graduates in archival studies as university archival experts. This article is

also presented with this approach to be an example for setting up standard university archives in Iran or perhaps the Middle East.

History of Alzahra University

Alzahra University, founded in 1964 as "Girls' College," Alzahra University, is one of the prominent institutions of higher education in Iran dedicated to educating learned and lively women. Although limited to the few Translation Studies, Psychology, Secretarial Studies, and Housewifery majors during its early years of establishment, Girls' College gradually grew. In 1975 was officially expanded into a university with four independent faculties of Humanities and Literature, Management, Economics, and Sciences.

After the Islamic Revolution in Iran, it was renamed Alzahra University and continued to flourish in an enterprising and progressive spirit. During the past 40 years, the university has tremendously changed and developed and is now offering various degree programs at undergraduate and graduate levels.

Since 2013, educational and research services have been provided by the university's ten faculties viz Literature, Theology, Physical Education and Sport Sciences, Social Sciences and Economics, Education and Psychology, Mathematical Sciences, Biology, Engineering, Physics and Chemistry, and Arts. The two research centers of Women Studies and Economic Studies are also focused on doing cutting-edge research and educating future researchers. Alzahra's second campus has been recently found in the scenic city of Urmia.

There are currently around 10000 students studying 160 majors at the university. More than 380 full-time faculty members are also working in 49 departments that offer degree programs at bachelors, masters, and Ph.D. levels. Of all the faculty members, 50% are assistant professors, 35% associate professors, and 15% full professors.

Launch Alzahra University Archive

Formation of the Archives Committee

A professional committee was formed to establish the archive and museum of Alzahra University, as everything is done better with the group members' guidance. This committee is the

highest decision-making authority on the University archive and related records at Alzahra University and was created to guide and oversee launching the University archive and museum. The committee must approve all the bylaws, guidelines, and policies of the University Archives. The members of this committee are:

- Faculty Member of Alzahra University Information Science and Knowledge Department and Specialist in Archival Studies
- Head of Department of Information Science and Knowledge of Alzahra University
- Head of Alzahra University Central Library
- Head of the Faculty of Art at Alzahra University
- Head of Department of History at Alzahra University
- Alzahra University Department of Public Relations

It should be noted that the committee is obliged to regulate all its decisions by the laws and regulations of the National Iranian Recordation Council and Branch of the International Committee of University Museums in Iran.

The university has the following goals:

Alzahra University archive and museum supports the university's teaching and research mission by striving to preserve and gain access to permanently valuable university records and objects, collect accurate, credible, and complete university life documentation and promote the highest management standards for Alzahra University's current records and objects.

The purpose of collecting these records is to select valuable university records, to ensure the preservation of records and objects with the value have standard terms and availability following current and future rules and regulations for researchers.

It should be noted that the university archive and museum is managed and supported by the president of this university and its public relations management, and so its users are students, professors, and researchers.

The vision of Alzahra University archive and museum

Alzahra University has outlined in its short-term program the following perspectives:

- Provide effective and timely record and object management services to different departments and faculties of Alzahra University
- Expand Record Management Services to digitize records
- Providing services and responding effectively to information requests from management, colleges, and groups of researchers
- Create access to Alzahra University archive and museum collections through research forums, online resources, and social networks for researchers and stakeholders

Doing related research

With its student executive staff's help, the university all specializes in archival studies, facilitating the archiving committee's decision-making for science-based research. One of the researches in selecting suitable archive software and other research in the review of policies of the universities archives of the world to compose the policy of Alzahra University.

About the policy

The policy of university archives and museums reflects their goals, missions, activities, and visions. The policy of Alzahra University also includes explanations about the plans, mission, vision, and information about managing the records and objects of this archive from the stage of collection to dissemination and accessibility. Also, considering the importance of accessing the policy of archives and museums electronically and its impact on recognizing these centers globally, the Alzahra University archive and museum has placed its policy electronically in the form of generalities on its site. More details are provided below.

Policy formulation

Alzahra University, with the guidance of members of the University Archives Committee and in collaboration with its executive staff, has developed a policy that is being reviewed by the University archive and museum Committee. This policy has attempted to comply with national

records and object items, and international standards of policy. The things considered in this policy are as follows:

- Acquisition and evaluation of records and objects

Apart from records and objects from Alzahra University that are kept in the archive and museum, some records and objects are in possession of record centers, archives, museums, individuals, and other organizations that need to be called according to the instructions of Alzahra University. Procurement methods include donation, sale, exchange, and lending. University records also need to be reviewed and evaluated before entering the archive. The purpose of evaluating records is to recognize the archival records from the destroyed records that this activity causes in time, space, human resources, and cost.

- Arranging and describing records and objects

This process is important because of its direct impact on facilitating record and object retrieval by experts and researchers. In the procedure for records, the information of records in specific worksheets of each record (such as worksheets for photos, stamps, text and paper records, etc.), prepared according to ISAD standards, are entered by the expert. The same process is done for museum objects but according to the specific standards of museums.

- Record protection

The goals set by Alzahra University Museum and Archive for conservation include planning and policy-making on how to protect and maintain the university archive and museum building, equipment and archival and museum resources; creating a standard space and environment suitable for conservation and preservation of resources; The obsolescence of the university archive and the museum building is equipment and resources and disaster preparedness.

- Access to records and objects

One of the main reasons for keeping Alzahra University records and objects is to make the necessary arrangements for their use. On the other hand, access policies stand as a deterrent to the availability of full and free resources. To this end, the university archives design policies and procedures that, in addition to meeting research needs, also take care of records and objects. These policies also provide a framework.

- Oral History

The necessity of forming the oral history section of Alzahra University archive, including such things as recording the history of Alzahra University, strengthening the scientific position of Alzahra University and leading it in the region, serving Iranian culture, and regional recording history in various political, social, cultural and It is economical.

- Alzahra University Archive Crisis Management

Ways to deal with turmoil and crises to ensure the university's historical and cultural monuments' survival can be considered part of the Alzahra University archive and museum management strategy. Crisis management methods in the archive and museum are classified into the following four sections:

Step 1: Prevent the crisis.

Step 2: Planning Crisis Response Methods

Step 3: Crisis coping strategy

Stage 4: After the crisis (recycling of works), rehabilitation and reconstruction of damaged resources

Scope of Alzahra University archive and museum Collection

Alzahra University archive and museum strives to ensure the permanent preservation of historical records, objects, and other resources that reflect the university's roots, development, activities, and achievements of staff, faculty, students, and graduates. Therefore, the university archive and museum collect valuable records and objects that show the university's evolution, progress, decisions, and activities since 1946 in various fields. This collection includes (but is not limited to) the following:

-Reports(study trips, research projects, and award records, research done in laboratories and institutes related to the university)

- Administrative records include training programs and sample exam questions

- Class schedules, enrollment records, graduation lists

- All publications, newsletters, posters, catalogs, bulletins, yearbooks, student publications
- Sources in a specific format that record the activities and development of the university, such as audio, video, and multimedia productions
- Dissertations and records related to honor
- Museum items such as clothing, medals, commendation plaques as well as collections related to students and graduates
- Faculty articles or manuscript collections

Specialized human force

Alzahra University has specialized graduates in the field of archival studies. Therefore, he tried to use these people's skills and expertise as a museum and archive experts. This is one of the things that distinguishes the Alzahra university archive from other Iranian university recordation centers.

Museum and archive in the operational plan

To plan for implementing the goals and perspectives of the archives and museum of Alzahra University, this university has a unique table for this university's archives and museum in the presented operational plan. This helps to carry out this department's activities in a specific framework and provides the possibility of evaluating the programs' realization and the potential of comparison.

Table 1. operational Plan

Actions	Activities	Responsible for implementation
Creating and establish museum and archive	Collecting records and objects	University Public Relations Management
	Preparation of oral history	University Public Relations Management
	Provision of software and	University Public Relations

Actions	Activities	Responsible for implementation
	archival system	Management
	Create a museum website and archive	University Public Relations Management in collaboration with the Information Technology Unit
	Creating a suitable space for storing and protecting objects and records	University Public Relations Management in collaboration with the administrative and financial unit
	Holding exhibitions and workshops	University Public Relations Management

Allocate part of the university budget to equip archive and museum

The university budget program included a special section for the university archives and museum. This budget equips the archive and museum with security tools, perseveration equipment, and access and use of records and objects equipment. This particular section in the university budget can show the importance that Alzahra University attaches to its records and objects as part of its country's historical memory.

Creating Alzahra University archive and museum website

The archive and museum website of Alzahra University was created in the year 2020 to free access to university records and information and maximum communication with its users.

On this website, the university archive and museum policy, one of the essential factors in recognizing an archive and museum and its goals and activities, is available to users.

Informing about archival activities in the world, especially the activities and actions of the ICA, has been one of the goals of launching this website. In this website, a section has been placed as

a guide for donating records and objects, and its call has been announced on the university's social media, including the Instagram page of the archive and the museum.

Services

Alzahra University Archive and Museum is ready to provide services to staff, professors, students, and all researchers interested in using this center's records and objects. These services will include the following:

-Educational and research services

About the research, the university archives and museums are ready to respond in person and electronically at the request of researchers to access and use the available records and objects.

-Public Services

To raise public awareness of this center's activities, the Alzahra University archive and museum have taken steps such as holding a workshop and a weekly exhibition of records and objects. Due to the importance of social media in today's technology world, this center has created a page on Instagram. These measures are described below.

Exhibiting

Alzahra University held a weeklong exhibition on National Records Day before the covid 19 outbreak. The records shown in this exhibition are as follows:

- Written Records
- Photos
- Map

An exhibition of university museum objects was also held for one week on the World Museums Day occasion. Items exhibited at the fair included old University equipment and honors, photo and film equipment, and laboratory equipment.

On the other hand, due to the world's current situation for the pandemic of the outbreak of covid19, the university has launched a virtual exhibition on the site and has made many of its records and objects visible to users.

Holding a virtual workshop

Due to the importance of continuous training and learning of archival specialists and the benefits of transferring experience and knowledge to individuals, the Alzahra University archive and museum planned to hold training workshops. Following the Covid 19 epidemic, the university decided to have a workshop on "electronic archives and crisis management." The workshop was held virtually on the Adobe Connect platform.

Activity on social media

Today, social media plays an important role in recognizing all organizations' activities and services, including museums and archives. Therefore, the archive and museum of Alzahra University has also created a page on Instagram⁴. The content of this page includes informing about the events held on the subject of archives and museums in this university and all archive and museum centers in Iran and the world. This page also introduces its records and objects to users. On the other hand, this page is an excellent place to provide a call to collect and receive records and objects from people.

Using the Document Archive System

Given that archival records are transferred to the archive over thirty to forty years, these records' preservation and organization are the most important.

On the other hand, these records' availability is important for a university's various administrative departments as current records. Therefore, a system for archiving current and administrative records of the university is intended. In this software, records are sorted and

⁴ @aumusarch

sorted by topic. It also specifies the level of access to each record. It is worth noting that this system is designed to meet the documentary needs of Alzahra University and be used internally.

Implementation plan for the first full-archive and museum pilot software at the university

In Iran, most records and archive centers use library software with some archived items added, but in principle, all of them are library software. So Alzahra University planned to pilot software with archive and museum capabilities at the university. This software will become a fully archived and native software in time, based on archive and museum experts' consultation with software experts and archival and museum standards.

Discussion and Conclusion

Managing the university archives and museums are very important to produce records and objects that form part of any country's national memory. Alzahra University has also decided to launch a university archive and museum to have a rich and important history in creating the university archive and museum. Alzahra University's action in setting up the university archive and museum is a different and pioneering work in Iran and possibly the Middle East in complying with international archiving standards.

In this regard, as discussed above, the University archive and museum Committee is made up of experts who have defined goals and perspectives for themselves. It seems that establishing a specialized committee in this field will increase the supervision of the better implementation of this activity and achieve the defined goals.

As mentioned above, related research has been undertaken to set up the university archive and museum. It seems that conducting scientific research by carefully examining each activity's details and examining its feasibility can facilitate activity and prevent rework.

It was also noted that the university had developed a policy for its archive and museum activities. It seems that a well-established policy is a practical requirement for implementing the Alzahra University archive and museum establishing program. Also, the existence of a formulated policy enables all people to use this policy.

On the other hand, it seems that the holding of an exhibition containing historical records and objects of Alzahra University, so to informing about the history of the university and the records and objects contained therein, was an introduction to the launch of the university archive and museum.

Also, creating a website for the university archives and museum and the free access to records and objects is the important measure of this archive and museum. Setting up a virtual record and object exhibition during the covid 19 outbreak is an attempt to coordinate with other university archives' actions around the world.

Given that archival record management is an introduction to preserving university archives, it seems Alzahra University uses a systematic archive that facilitates the search and access of current university administrative records that has an important role in managing university records.

From the point of use of proper archiving and museum software implemented according to archival and museum standards, it has a significant impact on the entire archiving process of a university's archive and museum. The presentation and implementation of a full archive software at Alzahra University is also an important step towards moving forward in archival studies in Iran.

Suggestions for setting up other Iranian university archives

- Researching university archives in the Middle East
- Develop a single standard policy for Iranian university archives
- Make museum and archive policy available electronically
- Use of graduates in the field of archival and museum studies in Iranian museums and university archives

Sources

Princeton University Records Management. (2018). *Benefits of Records*

Management Retrieved 2018, May 8, from

<https://records.princeton.edu/records-management-manual/records-management-concepts-definitions/benefits-records-management>

Society of American Archivists. (1999). *Guidelines for College and University Archives*. Retrieved 2018, May 20, from

<https://www2.archivists.org/book/export/html/14800>

The University of Michigan. (2014). *Records Policy and Procedures Manual* Retrieved 2018, May 8, from

https://bentley.umich.edu/wpcontent/uploads/2016/07/records_policy_and_manual_REV_09-01-2014.pdf

Zaker Salehi, GH.(2004). *Iranian University* .Tehran: Kavir.